

PEDIOCIN
PL- Surface – 2922.75

Lipoprotein (Lipo Xc)
PL- Surface – 25661.1

Molecular docking

PL- Surface – 22889.5

PL- Surface – 23338.64

PL- Surface – 23040.06

PL- Surface – 23271.14

